

Substituted Aryl-Hydroxamic Acids—A Study—Part—I The Synthesis of N-Phenyl Salicylhydroxamic Acids

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Substituted acetyl salicyloyl chlorides were condensed with β -phenyl hydroxyl amine in the presence of aqueous sodium acetate, sodium bicarbonate buffer; products obtained were characterised as N-phenyl acetyl salicylhydroxamic acids which on mild hydrolysis gave N-phenyl salicylhydroxamic acids.

A fairly detail information about the synthesis and chemical behaviour of salicylhydroxamic acids is available in literature. They are used as starting materials for the synthesis of 2-hydroxybenzoxazoles¹, 3-hydroxy benzisoxazoles² and N-hydroxy-1, 3-benzoxazine-4-ones³. However, very little is known about the synthesis of N-substituted salicylhydroxamic acids⁴. They are likely to serve as starting materials for the synthesis of N-substituted benzisoxazole-3-ones and other oxygen-nitrogen heterocyclic ring systems. Like N-phenyl benzhydroxamic acids they may have the potentialities as good analytical reagents⁵ N-phenyl salicylhydroxamic acids closely resembles-anilide-a textile fungicide⁶ and by virtue of the presence of N-OH group N-phenyl-salicylhydroxamic acid may exhibit some marked fungicidal activity. In view of these possibilities it was decided to develop a method for the synthesis of N-substituted salicylhydroxamic acids and also to study their chemical behaviour. This paper deals with the study of some N-phenylsalicyl hydroxamic acids.

Ghosh and Bhattacharya⁴ studied the condensation of salicyloyl chloride with β -phenylhydroxylamine using Bambergor method and reported the formation of N-phenylsalicylhydroxamic acid in very low yield. The most probable reason for the low yield of N-phenyl salicylhydroxamic acid appears to be the tendency of salicyloyl chloride to undergo intermolecular esterification to form di, tri and poly salicylides⁷. Formation of salicylides is favoured by both acids and bases.

It was thought that if acetyl salicyloyl chloride is used in place of salicyloyl chloride, the possibilities of salicylides formation will be eliminated. Acetyl salicyloyl chloride would, therefore, condense smoothly with β -phenyl hydroxylamine to give N-phenylacetylsalicylhydroxamic acid, which on mild alkaline hydrolysis would give N-phenylsalicylhydroxamic acids in very good yields.

Acetyl salicyloyl chloride(I) was, therefore, condensed with β -phenyl hydroxylamine in the presence of aqueous sodium acetate, sodium bicarbonate buffer.

Product obtained was hydrolysed with 1 N sodium hydroxide.

The compound obtained was found to be identical with the N-phenylsalicylhydroxamic acid reported by Ghosh and Bhattacharya⁴. Yield was found to be 80%. Adopting this new procedure, substituted acetyl

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND YIELDS OF N-PHENYL ACETYL SALICYLHYDROXAMIC ACIDS (II A-G) AND N-PHENYL SALICYL HYDROXAMIC ACIDS (III A-G).

II.	R	Melting point (°C)	Yield %
a)	H	118	80
b)	3-methyl	99	66
c)	4-chloro	131	70
d)	4-iodo	143	72
e)	5-chloro	148	78
f)	5-bromo	140	80
g)	5-iodo	124	76
III.			
a)	H	107	78
b)	3-methyl	113	60
c)	4-chloro	112-113	73
d)	4-iodo	127	64
e)	5-chloro	127	75
f)	5-bromo	131	70
g)	5-iodo	150	69

salicyloyl chlorides(I) were condensed with β -phenyl hydroxylamine. In all the cases studied, it was found that condensation was very smooth and free of side reactions. Yield of N-phenylsalicylhydroxamic acids varied over a range of 60-80%. Table 1 describes physical constants of the compounds synthesised.

Properties and structures: The condensation products of acetyl salicyloyl chlorides(I) and phenyl hydroxylamine are weak acids and dissolve in dilute sodium hydroxide as well as in dilute ammonia. Alcoholic solution of these compounds gives purple coloration with ferric chloride. The solubility in alkali and purple coloration with ferric chloride are indication of -C-N-OH grouping in these compounds. IR

spectra of these compounds show bands due to OH ($3340-3360\text{ cm}^{-1}$), ester carbonyl ($\sim 1780-90\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and amide carbonyl ($\sim 1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$). On the basis of these evidences these compounds are represented as N-phenyl salicylhydroxamic acids(II). Prolonged action of alkali on N-phenylsalicylhydroxamic acid hydrolyses the o-acetyl group to phenolic -OH. IR spectra of hydrolysed products show bands due to -OH ($\sim 3050-3160\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and amide carbonyl ($\sim 1630-1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$); ester carbonyl band was found to be absent. Alkaline solution of N-phenylsalicylhydroxamic acids show blue fluorescence when exposed to U. V. radiations. The fluorescence is very much similar to that of salicylanide, this is an additional evidence supporting the presence of -C-N< link in these compounds. Products

obtained by the alkaline hydrolysis are, therefore, represented as N-phenylsalicylhydroxamic acids(III).

Experimental

(a) *General procedure for the synthesis of N-phenyl acetyl salicylhydroxamic acids (II a-g).*

In a three necked round bottom flask, equipped with a mechanical stirrer and a dropping funnel was placed a solution of 0.15 mole sodium acetate and 0.1 mole of sodium bicarbonate in 200 ml of water. The flask was immersed in ice-salt bath and solution was stirred mechanically. When the solution was cooled to 5° , the solution of 0.06 mole of β -phenyl hydroxylamine in 100 ml ether was introduced in the flask. When the reaction mixture in flask was cooled to -5° or below, the solution of 0.05 mole of acetyl salicyloyl chloride(I) in 100 ml of anhydrous ether was introduced in flask through the tap funnel, at such a rate that the temperature of the reaction mixture was below 0°

throughout the course of addition. After the addition of acetyl salicyloyl chloride was over stirring was continued for about 1 hour. The solid obtained was filtered off, washed with water and finally with 20 ml of ether*. It was then suspended in 100 ml of water and the suspension was acidified with dil. acetic acid. The solid was filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from 50% ethanol.

(b) *General method for the preparation of N-phenyl salicylhydroxamic acids (III a-g).*

0.05 mole of N-phenylacetyl salicylhydroxamic acid(II) was suspended in 50 ml of water and 0.1 mole sodium hydroxide was added to it. Reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 2 hours, then it was neutralised with dil. HCl, precipitate obtained was filtered off and crystallised from 30% ethanol.

It is, therefore, necessary to extract the ethereal layer of filtrate with sodium hydroxide. In this process of extraction acetyl group is hydrolysed to phenolic OH. Product obtained after neutralisation of sodium hydroxide extract is, therefore, the appropriate N-phenyl salicylhydroxamic acid rather than acetyl derivative.

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Some N-phenyl acetyl Salicyl hydroxamic acids are appreciably soluble in ether.

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